

A NUMERICAL APPROACH FOR THE FAILURE ANALYSIS OF TEXTILE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The paper presents a numerical approach to evaluate the mechanical behaviour up to failure of textile composites and the validation of the method against experiments.

The main assumption is the periodic distribution of the reinforcements in the composite. This allows us to exploit the theoretical concepts of the homogenization theory for periodic media (see e.g. [1]). The model is based on two levels of homogenization. The first level concerns the warp and weft yarns considered as unidirectional fibre reinforced composites with a fibre volume fraction equal to the packing density. Their mechanical properties are obtained by numerical analyses of a representative volume following the approach described in [2]. The second homogenization level is applied at a representative volume of the textile composite that is modelled by means of a three-dimensional finite elements. The assumed material periodicity is taken into account imposing kinematic boundary conditions [3]. According to this procedure, the parameters necessary to describe the problem are limited to the geometry of the reinforcement and to the mechanical properties of the components (matrix and fibres).

The macroscopic behaviour up to failure is investigated assuming a Tsai-Hill like failure domain for the homogenized reinforcements. The progressive damage of the yarns is followed by a procedure involving the stiffness matrix elements degradation when the stress state in the current elements satisfies the assumed failure criterion. The elements of the stiffness matrix to be reduced depend on the failure mechanism of the yarns [4].

KEYWORDS: textile composites, homogenization, finite elements, failure.

INTRODUCTION

The popularity of textile composites is increasing after the initial application in high-performance fields such as aerospace and sporting goods. Recently, they have found application in automotive and construction industries thank to the significant reduction of manufacturing cost and acceptable mechanical properties. The development of different manufacturing techniques allows the production of low cost textile composites. In particular, resin transfer moulding (RTM) is regarded as one of the most promising production process that ensure regularity and geometrical stability of the fabric reinforcements in the realization of complex shapes and large components.

The peculiarities of textile composites confer practical interest in the prediction and optimisation of their mechanical features. The prediction of the mechanical properties of textile composites is not a simple task due to the complex architectures of the reinforcements. Their mechanical behaviour is has

been item of several research activities by different approaches. In particular the investigations can be grouped in three main methodologies: experimental [5, 6]; analytical [7, 8] and numerical [3, 9].

In this paper an approach belonging to the last category is presented assuming two main hypotheses: (i) regular distribution of the fibres in the yarns; (ii) regular arrangement of the reinforcing yarns in the composites. In this context, the homogenization theory for heterogeneous periodic materials, developed by Suquet [1], is applied at two different scales (Fig. 1). The first scale deals with the yarns considered as unidirectional composites. The second scale aims to provide the macroscopic behaviour of the textile composite material in which the yarns are described through a homogenized material obtained by the first scale modelling. Two representative volumes (RV) are considered in the two phases of the analysis (Fig. 1). In the first scale a RV including a single fibre and the surrounding matrix are considered, assuming a hexagonal distribution. In the second scale a RV including the homogenized yarns and the matrix are investigated.

The macroscopic behaviour of the material up to failure is simulated following the damage evolution by a procedure involving the stiffness matrix degradation when an assumed failure criterion is satisfied.

The macroscopic behaviour of a glass plane weave textile composite is examined and the numerical results are compared to experimental tests performed by the authors and by Ganesh et alii [10].

Fig. 1: Scheme of the two-scale homogenization procedure: from the textile composite to the mechanically equivalent homogenized material.

PROBLEM FORMULATION AND HOMOGENIZATION PROCEDURE

A three-dimensional numerical analysis of textile composites is developed in the framework of the homogenization theory for periodic media [1]. The main hypotheses are: regular distribution of the fibres in the yarns; regular arrangement of the reinforcing yarns in the composites and a perfect link between fibres (yarns) and matrix. The last hypothesis is a limitation and could be removed introducing interfaces at the two scale levels to transmit forces both between the fibres and the matrix in the yarns and between the yarns and the matrix.

The macroscopic constitutive law describes the relation between macroscopic stresses and strains (Σ , \mathbf{E}), defined as volumetric averages of the relevant microscopic variables ($\sigma(\mathbf{x})$, $\varepsilon(\mathbf{x})$) that are functions

of the position vector \mathbf{x} in the representative volume (RV) (bold symbols denote matrices and vectors). This law has to be determined in incremental form solving the problem:

$$\text{div} \dot{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \mathbf{0} \quad \text{in } V; \quad \dot{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = F(\dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}(\tilde{\mathbf{u}})) \quad \text{in } V \quad (1a,b)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{u}} = \mathbf{u} - \dot{\mathbf{E}} \cdot \mathbf{x} \quad V\text{-periodic}; \quad \dot{\mathbf{t}} = \dot{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \cdot \mathbf{n} \quad \text{anti-periodic on } \partial V \quad (1c,d)$$

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}} = \frac{1}{V} \int_V \dot{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} dV; \quad \dot{\mathbf{E}} = \frac{1}{V} \int_V \dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}} dV \quad (1e,f)$$

where ∂V and V indicate the boundary and the volume of the RV; \mathbf{n} is the outward unit-normal to ∂V . Eqn. (1a) is the microscopic equilibrium equation; eqn. (1b) represents the microscopic incremental constitutive law while eqn. (1c) and eqn. (1d) are the periodic kinematics and static boundary conditions respectively. The definition of the macroscopic quantities $(\boldsymbol{\Sigma}, \mathbf{E})$ is expressed by eqns. (1e,f).

In order to reproduce the periodicity of the heterogeneous material, in terms of kinematic quantities, the following general relation of the displacement field (1c) holds:

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{u}^0 + \boldsymbol{\Omega} \cdot \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{x} + \tilde{\mathbf{u}}(\mathbf{x}) \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{u}^0 represents a rigid displacement of the RV and $\boldsymbol{\Omega}$ is the anti-symmetric tensor related to the small rigid rotation of the RV. The pure strain modes of the RV are described by the last two terms in (2): a constant term (the macroscopic strain \mathbf{E}) and a V -periodic term, with zero average value, associated with the V -periodic part $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}$ of the microscopic displacement field.

The incremental problem (1) is solved at two scale levels by means of the displacement formulation of the finite element method. The first scale level deals with the yarns considered as unidirectional fiber reinforced composites, while the second scale level considers a textile composite material in which the yarns are described through a homogenized material obtained by the first level modelling.

The main task to implement problem (1) in a FE code is the assignment of the boundary conditions to ensure that the displacement field complies with eqn. (2). Details on the boundary conditions applied in the first scale modelling of the present approach are contained in ref. [2]. On the other hand, the periodic displacement boundary conditions applied in the second scale level are defined as follow [3]. Referring to the RV singled out from a textile composite in Fig. 2a, such conditions can be written as:

$$\mathbf{u}^H - \mathbf{u}^K = \mathbf{u}^J - \mathbf{u}^Y \quad (3a)$$

$$\mathbf{u}^P - \mathbf{u}^T = \mathbf{u}^A - \mathbf{u}^F \quad (3b)$$

where J and Y are one of the midpoints pairs (A, C) , (B, D) ; H and K are points corresponding in the periodicity belonging to the sides $x_1=d_1/2$ and $x_1=-d_1/2$ respectively if (A, C) are considered, or belonging to the sides $x_2=d_2/2$ and $x_2=-d_2/2$ if (B, D) are considered (see Fig. 2b). In Eqn. (3b), P is any point on the side $x_3=0$ and T is the corresponding point on the side $x_3=h$.

Fig. 2: (a) the RV geometry of a textile composite and FE model of the reinforcement; (b) characteristic points of the finite element model.

Accounting for the general expression of the displacement field (2) and the periodicity condition (3a,b), the macroscopic displacement gradient becomes linked to some displacement components on ∂V , namely:

$$\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{\Omega} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{u_1^A - u_1^C}{d_1} & \frac{u_1^B - u_1^D}{d_2} & \frac{u_1^F - u_1^A}{h} \\ \frac{u_2^A - u_2^C}{d_1} & \frac{u_2^B - u_2^D}{d_2} & \frac{u_2^F - u_2^A}{h} \\ \frac{u_3^A - u_3^C}{d_1} & \frac{u_3^B - u_3^D}{d_2} & \frac{u_3^F - u_3^A}{h} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Rigid translations of the model are suppressed by prescribing $\mathbf{u}^O = \mathbf{0}$ (see Fig. 2b). Rigid rotations can be avoided by imposing the skew symmetric tensor $\mathbf{\Omega}$ to vanish, setting:

$$\frac{d_1}{d_2} u_1^B - \frac{d_1}{d_2} u_1^D + u_2^C - u_2^A = 0 \quad (5a)$$

$$\frac{d_1}{h} u_1^F - \frac{d_1}{h} u_1^A + u_3^C - u_3^A = 0 \quad (5b)$$

$$\frac{d_2}{h} u_2^F - \frac{d_2}{h} u_2^A + u_3^D - u_3^B = 0 \quad (5c)$$

The six components of the symmetric tensor \mathbf{E} can be explicitly written as:

$$E_{11} = \frac{u_1^A - u_1^C}{d_1}; \quad E_{22} = \frac{u_2^B - u_2^D}{d_2}; \quad E_{33} = \frac{u_3^F - u_3^A}{h}; \quad (6a,b,c)$$

$$E_{12} = \frac{u_2^A - u_2^C}{d_1}; \quad E_{13} = \frac{u_3^A - u_3^C}{d_1}; \quad E_{23} = \frac{u_3^B - u_3^D}{d_2} \quad (6d,e,f)$$

Eqns (6) provide the kinematic boundary conditions to simulate any prescribed macroscopic strain through only some free nodal displacement components ($u_1^A, u_2^A, u_3^A, u_1^C, u_2^C, u_3^C, u_2^B, u_3^B, u_2^D, u_3^D, u_3^F$). In the numerical simulations macroscopic strain components are prescribed and the macroscopic stress tensor is evaluated by the volumetric averages (1e,f) of the microscopic counterparts in the Gauss integration points.

FAILURE PREDICTION

The progressive damage of the textile composite is studied in the analysis at the second scale. The Tsai-Hill failure criteria is assumed for the anisotropic homogenized yarns [11] while the isotropic matrix complies with von Mises criterion. The strength parameters of the homogenized yarns for Tsai-Hill domain are evaluated in the first scale modelling.

A simple degradation procedure is applied to evaluate the damage in the yarns up to a complete failure. When the stress state in a element satisfies the assumed failure criterion its stiffness matrix elements are dropped down according to the failure mechanism involved. The considered failure mechanics were presented also by Zako et al. [4]. Four possible damage modes are depicted in Table 1. Mode 1 represents the fibre breakage (being 1 the fibre direction); Modes 2 and 3 are due to transverse failure by normal stress and Modes 13, 23, 12 provides shear cracking.

The activation of a failure mode is assumed to depend on the maximum stress-strength ratio. The correlation between damage modes and stress-strength ratios is detailed in Table 1 where F^t , F^c , F^s are the tensile, compressive and shear strength parameters of the yarns (in the numerical analyses is assumed $F^t = F^c$).

Table 1: damage modes for yarns and maximum stress-strength ratio correlation.

Damage mode	Mode 1 			
Maximum stress-strength ratio	$\frac{\sigma_1^2}{F_1^t F_1^c}$	$\frac{\sigma_2^2}{F_2^t F_2^c}$ or $\left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{F_{12}^s}\right)^2$	$\frac{\sigma_3^2}{F_3^t F_3^c}$ or $\left(\frac{\tau_{13}}{F_{13}^s}\right)^2$	$\left(\frac{\tau_{23}}{F_{23}^s}\right)^2$

The components of the stiffness matrix to be reduced depend on the active damage mode. In Table 2 the reduction schemes associated to each damage mode are described. The damage parameter d is assumed equal to 0.01.

Table 2: reduced stiffness matrix components depending on the active damage mode.

Damage mode	Mode 1	Mode 2 or 12
reduced stiffness matrix	$\begin{bmatrix} dQ_{11} & dQ_{12} & dQ_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & Q_{22} & Q_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & Q_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ sym. & & & dQ_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ & & & & dQ_{55} & 0 \\ & & & & & Q_{66} \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & dQ_{12} & Q_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & dQ_{22} & dQ_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & Q_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ sym. & & & dQ_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ & & & & Q_{55} & 0 \\ & & & & & dQ_{66} \end{bmatrix}$
Damage mode	Mode 3 or 13	Mode 23

reduced stiffness matrix	$\begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & Q_{12} & dQ_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & Q_{22} & dQ_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & dQ_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & sym. & & Q_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ & & & & dQ_{55} & 0 \\ & & & & & dQ_{66} \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & dQ_{12} & dQ_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & dQ_{22} & dQ_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & dQ_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & sym. & & dQ_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ & & & & dQ_{55} & 0 \\ & & & & & dQ_{66} \end{bmatrix}$
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APPLICATION AND COMPARISONS

The numerical procedure is applied to simulate the ultimate behaviour of two balanced plane weave textile composites (G1 and G2) reinforced by glass fibres.

The mechanical properties of laminate G1 were determined by experimental characterisation carried out by the authors while the experimental data regarding the laminate G2 are detailed in [10].

The mechanical properties of the components (glass fibres and epoxy resin) are reported in Table 3.

Table 3: Mechanical properties of the components.

	G1		G2	
	Glass Fibres	Epoxy Matrix	Glass Fibres	Epoxy Matrix
Young modulus [MPa]	76000	2520	72000	3500
Poisson ratio	0.22	0.35	0.3	0.35
Tensile strength [MPa]	2000	50	1995	60

Fig. 3: the RV geometry of the textile composites and the FE model of the reinforcement in G1.

The geometries of the considered woven fabrics are periodic in the laminate plane. The RV shape considered is drawn in Fig. 3 and the geometric input are detailed in Table 4 where the packing density of the yarns (p_d) and the fibre volume fraction (c_f) are also reported. The elliptical shape of the cross-section and the longitudinal heart line of the yarns were reproduced on the basis of microscopic investigations [3] for material G1 and were taken from [10] for material G2.

Table 4: Geometric properties of the RV for the considered textile composites (see Fig. 3)

	$d_1 = d_2$ [mm]	$t_1 = t_2$ [mm]	$w_1 = w_2$ [mm]	$p_1 = p_2$ [mm]	h [mm]	p_d [%]	c_f [%]
G1	3.3	0.155	1.48	1.64	0.33	83	50.6
G2	1.5	0.048	0.45	0.75	0.15	74	23

The first homogenization step, regarding the yarns as unidirectional composites, was carried out assuming a hexagonal pattern of the fibre and taking the packing density of the yarn as fibre volume fraction. The numerical analyses provided the elastic and the strength properties of the homogenized transversally isotropic yarns reported in Table 5.

The finite element mesh employed in the second numerical homogenization step consisted of 2041 nodes, 9411 four-node tetrahedron elements for composite G1 and 913 nodes, 4379 elements for composite G2.

The numerical results obtained by the present approach are compared to the experimental data in Fig. 4 for the macroscopic tensile stress-strain relations. The numerical global properties of the textile composites are in agreement with the experiments even if the failure strain values predicted are lower than the experimental ones. This is probably due to an overestimation of the fibre volume fraction of the composites that provides stiffer material than the real ones.

CONCLUSIONS

A two-scale numerical modelling technique is presented for the prediction of the macroscopic mechanical behaviour up to failure of textile composite materials. The homogenization theory for periodic media was first applied to the yarns considered as unidirectional fiber reinforced composite then to the woven composite with homogenized yarns. The agreement between experimental and numerical results confirms the efficiency of the present approach, in spite of the initial two scale periodicity hypotheses. The approach may be easily implemented into commercial finite element codes and appears to be an efficient tool for design and optimization of textile composite materials.

Table 5: Mechanical properties of the transversally isotropic homogenized yarns (first scale modelling). 1 refers to the fibres direction; 2 and 3 to the directions transversal to the fibres.

	G1	G2
E_1 [MPa]	63500	54190
$E_2=E_3$ [MPa]	23160	18940
$\nu_{12}=\nu_{13}$	0.23	0.31
ν_{23}	0.31	0.36
$G_{12}=G_{13}$ [MPa]	8821	6960
G_{23} [MPa]	8446	6828
F_1^t [MPa]	1672	1492
$F_2^t = F_3^t$ [MPa]	179	65
$F_{12}^s = F_{13}^s$ [MPa]	337	300
F_{23}^s [MPa]	100	100

Fig. 4: Comparison of the macroscopic stress-strain behaviour by the present approach and experiments. Tensile tests for: (a) composite G1; (b) composite G2.

(a)

(b)

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